

Open, FAIR, and used: toxicology in the next 10 years

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Abstract

For toxicology to take advantage of modern science, and for risk assessment to meet societal needs, it needs to step up its open science practices. Here, I argue that FAIR and sustainability should not distract us (too much) from the bigger picture. And that with the risk of preaching to the choir; after all, to me, one key selling point of OpenTox has been their argument for open licensing. This presentation sketches a vision of where toxicology is heading (or should be) in the next 10 years, starting with open science achievements, a series of past research projects, and designs of running projects. The role of open data, open source, and open standards will be illustrated with activities in EU NanoSafetyCluster projects and the ELIXIR Toxicology Community.